

OCEAN ICE News – June 2026

OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to June's edition of OCEAN ICE News. We're excited to bring you the latest updates from the OCEAN ICE community.

In this issue, you'll meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on key activities, such as an OCEAN ICE Publication, and OCEAN ICE presented at EGU26 and highlighting April's Climate Coffee. We have some upcoming Climate Coffee's that you can register for in June. Don't forget to mark your calendars for the upcoming events where OCEAN ICE will be represented.

We hope you enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to sharing more in July!

Meet the Team: Kateryna Kovalets

Check out our latest 'Meet the Team' feature on Kateryna Kovalets, a PhD student in The Institute of Mathematical Machines and Systems Problems of the Ukraine National Academy of Science.

Read the feature on Kateryna [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN ICE Activities

OCEAN ICE Presented at EGU26 General Assembly

At the EGU 2026 General Assembly in Vienna in early May, an OCEAN ICE study by Feldmann et al. (<https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-5859>) was presented by WP6 co-lead Torsten Albrecht. The study reveals that the stability of Antarctica's ice sheets is far more sensitive to the rate of climate change than previously thought, especially when accounting for the Earth's visco-elastic response beneath the ice.

On May 3-May 8, with the support of OCEAN ICE, Dr. Zhetao Tan (ENS-PSL) had the honour to present his latest research on the "Growing Influence of Indian Ocean Waters in the South Atlantic Intermediate Layer over the last 30 years", in the session OS1.6 (Physical, biological and chemical evolution of high-latitude oceans: from past to future).

Read the full summary [here](#).

OCEAN ICE Publication: Meltwater Feedback Weakens Under Warming: New Insight from OCEAN ICE Research

A new study by Kreuzer et al. (2026, OCEAN ICE Contribution #32) reveals that a critical non-linear response in the Antarctic climate system, the meltwater–stratification feedback, becomes less effective under strong global warming.

This feedback loop, central to OCEAN ICE’s research, works as follows: meltwater from the Antarctic Ice Sheet freshens the surface ocean, increasing stratification and reducing vertical mixing. This traps heat below the surface, warming the ocean near ice shelves’ grounding lines and accelerating basal melting, a self-reinforcing cycle amplifying ice loss. However, the study finds that feedback strength depends on the climate state.

Read the full article [here](#).

OCEAN ICE Climate coffee – April

Climate Coffee with Jens Terhaar on Record Sea Surface Temperature Jump in 2023–2024

Over the past months, global sea surface temperatures (SSTs) have quietly done something quite important: they have returned to levels below those before the pronounced jump observed in 2023/24 (<https://climatereanalyzer.org/clim/ss...> Earlier this year, we published a study in Nature magazine <https://www.nature.com/articles/s4158...> showing that abrupt SST jumps of this magnitude can arise solely from internal climate variability, as climate models can simulate such events without invoking an external shock or a permanent system shift. A key feature of these simulated jumps is that they are transient - temperatures typically relax back to pre-jump levels about two years later. What is striking is that the real-world evolution has closely followed this pattern. Observed SSTs have now also returned to pre-jump levels, roughly two months later than the model range suggested. Given the small number of simulations with such high jumps (8 models), the range for the return remains uncertain, and a 2-month delay is well within uncertainty. The return of SSTs below pre-jump levels thus adds confidence to the interpretation that the 2023/24 jump may have been driven by internal variability rather than a fundamental reorganisation of the climate system. However, until we have observations over the next few years, we still cannot exclude a fundamental system shift. At the same time, the relatively late recovery may point toward a climate system that responds more strongly to forcing than many models currently suggest - in other words, a potentially higher equilibrium climate sensitivity (ECS) and stronger underlying warming. This interpretation aligns with another recent study of ours by Linus Vogt (<https://esd.copernicus.org/articles/1...>), which shows that many climate models simulate too little Antarctic sea ice compared to observations. Because Antarctic sea ice strongly affects how much heat the Southern Ocean absorbs, this bias can lead to an underestimation of ECS.

Taken together, these results highlight an important nuance: short-term climate variability can produce large, temporary excursions, but the climate system's background sensitivity still matters enormously for long-term warming. Understanding both - and not confusing one for the other - is crucial for interpreting recent extremes and for improving future projections. At the same time, recent events are a reminder of how little we still understand about the climate system, and how important it is to keep questioning, testing, and refining our models as new observations emerge.

Publication: Terhaar, J., Burger, F.A., Vogt, L. et al. Record sea surface temperature jump in 2023–2024 unlikely but not unexpected. Nature 639, 942–946 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-025-08...>

Climate Coffee

23 April 2026 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Jens Terhaar
(University Bern)

**Record sea surface temperature jump
in 2023–2024 unlikely but not
unexpected**

Danish Meteorological Institute **ECRA**

OCEAN:ICE

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the European Union

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch, the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Upcoming Events

Climate Coffee

We have an upcoming Climate Coffee in June, make sure you register for all of them through the link on [OCEAN ICE](#).

Climate Coffee with Torsten Albrecht on Mapping tipping risks from Antarctic ice basins under global warming

18 June 2026, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

Thu 18 June 2026 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST

Online

Torsten Albrecht

(Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research)

Mapping tipping risks from Antarctic ice basins under global warming

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

One Ocean: What Polar and Atlantic Change Means for Europe

A science-policy event on emerging ocean and climate risks

Climate-driven changes in the Atlantic Ocean, the Southern Ocean and the Arctic are creating growing risks for Europe's climate, economy, infrastructure and long-term resilience.

The event titled "One Ocean: What polar and Atlantic change means for Europe" will bring together scientists, policymakers and stakeholders to explore the latest research on these interconnected changes, including new findings on the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation, polar regions and their implications for Europe.

The event is co-organised by the Horizon Europe projects OCEAN ICE and EPOC, and hosted by the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences.

Event details

Date: Friday 11 September 2026

Time: 12:30–16:30

Networking lunch/finger food: from 11:30

Location: Natural History Museum, Brussels, and online

Registration: <https://www.eventbrite.dk/e/a-story-of-penguins-floats-and-balloons-in-antarctica-tickets-1990394996013>

Read more information about the event [here](#).

A story of penguins, floats, and balloons in Antarctica

OCEAN:ICE

The National Antarctic Scientific Center,
Ukraine, presents its work in the Southern Ocean

11 September 2026
Starts at 5 pm until 6.30 pm

Museum of Natural Sciences
Rue Vautier 29, 1000 Brussels

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STATE INSTITUTION
NATIONAL ANTARCTIC
SCIENTIFIC CENTER
Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine

Danish Meteorological Institute

Happening Soon

OCEAN ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- o 23rd – 27th June 2026, [IGS Meeting](#), Dartmouth, US
- o 8th-9th August 2026, [SOOS Annual Meeting](#), Oslo, Norway
- o 8th -19th August 2026, [SCAR Open Science Conference & Meetings](#), Norway, Oslo
- o 17th - 19th August 2026, [FRISP Meeting 2026](#), Sweden, Kristineberg
- o 24th-29th August 2026, [The Polar Climate Space hackathon](#), Ljungskile, Sweden

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

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Stay up to date with OCEAN ICE on our following channels:

www.ocean-ice.eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

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[OCEAN ICE \(@oceaniceeu.bsky.social\) — Bluesky](#)

Who is OCEAN ICE?

OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

OCEAN:ICE

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